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- Poetry
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“STEPPING STONE”

Ten years ago, I wanted to work here as a teacher. Now I work here. At that time, I was just a regular office worker who didn't talk to students or even my coworkers very much. Days went by quickly, and my biggest dream came true. From being a regular clerk to being a teacher. From a regular employee to a lively teacher.

Even though I have a lot of flaws, I am now in my 10th year as a Junior and Grade School Music and Arts Teacher and my 15th year working for this school. People often tell me that I already own one of the posts in this school, and I'm proud of it. I think they value what I bring to the table, not just as a music and arts teacher but also as an employee who is passionate, honest, and afraid of the Lord. I think I can say that I've really taken in our core values of Communion, Service, and Excellence.

There are a lot of surprises and problems that come up when you're a teacher. But thanks to God's mercy and guidance and the help of my family and coworkers, I'm still here. We are shaping, influencing, and guiding young learners, who will be our future leaders. I'm still here, studying for myself and for my students.

Now I'm working on my master's degree in Educational Management. This new path is hard. I work as a teacher from Monday to Friday, but sometimes weekends are also considered school days because of activities. This has taught me how to use my time wisely, such as by keeping my workspace and materials in order, putting tasks in order of importance and urgency, setting deadlines, using resources wisely, and not putting things off.

I have had trouble managing my time. I like to go to new places, cafés, and attractions all the time. I've actually been to a lot of coffee shops, museums, and other places in Rizal and even beyond with my friends. As a friend, I say yes to invitations without thinking. They even call me "kaladkarin." But when I started grad school, I had to say no to these invitations a lot. My friends were surprised at first, but I told them about my situation as a MaEd student. They were happy for me and got it. When they don't want to go out with me, they send me coffee through Grab or Lalamove and call me on video instead.

I've learned how to plan and organize things from this course and from the whole summer class. This journey is a long one, but I think I will keep learning more about how to run a school and my own classroom as an adviser. St. Ignatius of Loyola said, "He who goes about to reform the world must begin with himself,

or he loses his labor." Getting ready for change starts with being organized and having self-control. The things I've learned in this class will help me as a teacher for a long time to come. This is lifelong learning, which is the first step I need to take to grow in my career. In fact, education will be in harmony if all teachers and administrators work together and do important administrative tasks like planning and organizing on a regular basis.

